

Strategic Planning and Growth of Women-Owned Small and Medium Enterprises in Daraja Mbili Market, Kisii County

Alice Nyakerario Makini¹, Dr Jane Omwenga²

^{1,2}Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Nairobi, Kenya

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6566515>

Published Date: 20-May-2022

Abstract: The study sought to establish the relationship between Strategic Planning and Growth of Women Owned Small and medium Enterprises in Kisii. Specifically, the study sought to determine the influence of: Organizational envisioning, environmental awareness, strategy options, and planning instruments on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja Mbili market Kisii County. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The target population included women owners/managers of enterprises at Daraja market. Data gotten showed the target population of 450 women owned enterprises. These enterprises were categorised into four different sectors/trades: Textile, Metal fabrication, Woodwork and Other trades. Stratified random sampling technique was used to establish and access the study sample of 158 respondents. Primary and secondary data was collected. Primary data was collected by structured questionnaires. Secondary data was collected from relevant government institutional documents and publications in referred journals. The collected data was edited, coded and entered into SPSS version 16.0 software for analysis. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. In particular, Regression Analysis was used to investigate the relationships between hypothesized variables. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to investigate whether independent variables had combined effect on the dependent variable. The findings were presented using figures and tables. The study found out that SME owners have a vision in their minds but not shared amongst organizational members. This is reflected in their lack of a well stated and communicated vision, mission and value statements. However, the study found enterprise owners/managers to be well aware of the prevailing environment. The study also found that SME's tend to rely on differentiation and focus/niche business strategy more than on cost leadership and innovation strategies. The study further established that about three quarter of entrepreneurs reported to not having any planning instrument. In conclusion, the study provides evidence that strategic planning does influence growth of SME. The study recommends institutional support to this sector in the form of business development services to motivate this sector to grow. The study also recommends to SME through their associations to build networks both within and without to help members learn best practices for sustainable growth

Keywords: Organizational envisioning, environmental awareness, strategy options, planning instruments on growth.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Academicians and professional managers are increasingly acknowledging the importance of strategic planning as a major activity of organisational management. Over the last few decades, the literature on small business planning has grown significantly. With a few notable exceptions, many scholars have advocated for small businesses to use strategic planning as a critical tool for improved performance.

Strategic planning refers to the processes that firms use to develop strategies that may help them perform better (Tapinos, et.al, 2005). A long time horizon, formality, the use of planning instruments, and frequent plan control are all important aspects of strategic planning. Strategic planning can improve performance by generating relevant information, improving understanding of the critical environment, and reducing uncertainty (Hodgetts and Kuratko, 2001). Strategic awareness entails the ability to assess the overall implications of any given change. This entails not only being aware of the immediate implications of any new development, but also reflecting on the long-term consequences. To gain insights into the strategic awareness of owner managers who had projections for their strategic action, they were asked to discuss the following topics: the implications of their future projects on their time and lifestyle; the firm's capital assets; employees; raw materials; and marketing.

Many studies have concluded that business failure is primarily the result of an organization's failure to plan. According to Deya, Omwenga, and Muturi, (2015), "a business has no sustainable basis for creating and maintaining a competitive edge in the marketplace without a clearly defined strategy." Various empirical studies that show a link between strategic planning and firm success support this viewpoint (Gibson et al., 2002). As a result, strategic planning is a critical research topic for organisational success. According to studies, the high failure rate among small businesses, particularly start-ups, can be attributed to a lack of formal business planning (Castrogiovanni, 1996)

According to studies, planning is important not only for large organisations but also for SMEs (Rue and Ibrahim, 1998). Berman et al. (1997) discovered that firms that plan outperform firms that do not plan out. According to Shikuku, and Omwenga, (2015), planning lays the groundwork for developing the strategic capabilities required for high performance. Business success is not guaranteed by planning. However, when strategic planning is used, many of the contributing factors to business failures can be predicted and effectively addressed during the early stages of small business development, lowering the failure rate for small businesses.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are a diverse group. SMEs can be found in a wide range of business activities, from a single artisan producing agricultural implements for the village market to a small sophisticated engineering or software firm selling in overseas markets and a medium-sized automotive parts manufacturer selling to multinational automakers in both domestic and foreign markets. The owners may or may not be poor; the businesses operate in a variety of markets (urban, rural, local, national, regional, and international); they have varying levels of skills, capital, sophistication, and growth orientation; and they may be in the formal or informal economy (Sije, Omwenga, & Iravo, 2016). The statistical definition of SMEs varies by country (Badrinath et al. 1997) and is typically based on the number of employees, sales value, and/or asset value. The most commonly used variable is the number of employees due to its ease of collection. With a few exceptions, such as Japan (300 employees) and the United States, the EU and a large number of OECD (Bannock et al. 2002), transition and developing countries set the upper limit for the number of employees in SMEs at 200-250. (500 employees).

As a result, where the formal sector thrived, the small enterprise sector was expected to thrive, while a crisis in the formal sector would lead to a crisis in the small enterprise sector. As a result, the small-business sector was expected to grow in tandem with the formal sector (Pederson, 2005). According to the Economic Survey 2004, employment in the SMEs sector increased from 4.2 million in 2000 to 5.5 million in 2003, accounting for 75.3 percent of all workers in 2003. The sector accounts for up to 18.4% of the country's Gross Domestic Product (CBS et al, 1999). As a result, the SMEs sector should be viewed not only as a provider of goods and services, but also as a driver of competition and innovation, fostering the enterprise culture required for private sector development and industrialization (Republic of Kenya, 2005).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Given that the majority of strategic management research has thus far focused on large enterprises, many scholars have recently recognised the need to apply these concepts in the context of small businesses as well (Perry, 2001; Gibson and Cassar, 2005). The most important determinant of firm growth is strategy (Weinzimmer, 2000). Strategy content and process (strategic planning) are widely regarded as one of the factors that contribute to the growth of small businesses (Rue and Ibrahim, 1998; Kraus et al., 2008). Studying strategic processes in growth-oriented firms thus contributes to our understanding of the growth process, which has broader economic implications because growth-oriented firms are a major source of job creation (Parker, 2004; Valliere, 2006). However, little is known about how Micro and Small business managers or owners perceive strategy and strategic planning, and thus what strategy means to them in their day-to-day operations. As a result, this status in micro and small businesses provides impetus for research into the impact of strategic planning on their growth.

1.3 Objectives of study

1.3.1 General Objective

The study sought to establish the relationship between Strategic Planning and Growth of Women Owned Small and Medium Enterprises in Kisii.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

Specifically the study sought:

1. To determine the influence of Organizational Envisioning on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja market kisii county, Kenya.
2. To examine the influence of Environmental Awareness on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja market kisii county, Kenya.
3. To establish the influence of Strategy Options on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja market kisii county, Kenya.
4. To determine the influence of Planning Instruments on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja market kisii county, Kenya.

1.4 Research Hypotheses

1. H_0 : Organizational Envisioning has no significant influence on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja market kisii county, Kenya.
2. H_0 : Environmental Awareness has no significant influence on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja market kisii county, Kenya.
3. H_0 : There is no significant influence of Strategy Options on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja market kisii county, Kenya.
4. H_0 : Planning Instruments have no significant influence on growth of Women owned Small and Medium Enterprises at Daraja market kisii county, Kenya.

1.5. Significance of study

According to the Economic Survey of 2009, the Small Enterprise Sector or Informal Sector provided approximately 80% of total employment and contributed more than 92 percent of new jobs created in 2008. As a result, the sector is critical to job creation, income generation, and the industrialization of the country as envisioned in the Vision 2030 blueprint. As far as developing training materials and areas of focus for the group, this study will be critical to the various institutions mandated to drive the MSE agenda in Kenya (MSE Authority). The study will provide a status report on the extent to which strategic plans are used by Micro and Small Enterprises in Kisumu in particular, and Kenya in general. The research will also contribute to a body of knowledge for future small business development researchers.

1.6. Scope of study

According to the research It was determined that strategic planning has an impact on MSE growth in Kenya. Women-owned MSEs in Kibuye Market, Kisumu County, Kenya, were given special attention by the Kibuye Jua Kali Association, which is registered with the Micro and Small Enterprise Authority (MSEA). Kibuye Market is Kisumu County's largest open-air consumer goods market, located along the Kisumu-Kakamega road about 1km from the city centre. The research took place in October of 2015.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The term "enterprise growth" refers to a company's progression from small to large, and from weak to strong. The meanings of development go beyond the meanings of growth, and they include not only the growth process of things, but also the generation stage that emerges from noting prior to growth, as well as the periodic process of the stage, such as the cycle process that repeats itself. However, compared to a simple scale extension, enterprise growth is a complex adjustment process. It is the process of balanced development from unbalance to balance, and from lower balance to

higher balance, and it takes the balance adjustments of various relations in the interior and exterior of the enterprise as its essential character. As a result, enterprise growth is defined as a development process in which an enterprise maintains balanced and stable growth of total performance (including output, sales volume, profit, and asset gross) or realises large enhancements in total performance and development quality and level (Sun, 2004). Three connotations are contained in the meanings of enterprise growth. 1) The time property of business expansion. The long-term development tendency and process of an enterprise are observed, not the status of an enterprise at a specific time point, as the premise for analysing enterprise growth. 2) The dynamic property of business expansion. The expansion of a business is not a trouble-free process. Enterprise always transits from balance to unbalance during the growth process, with the result that it transits from unbalance to balance and from lower balance to higher balance through unbalance. 3) The unification of quantity and quality in business growth. The expansion of enterprise scale, such as sales volume, market share, production value, profit, and employee, embodies the increase in quantity. And the enhancement of enterprise quality, which includes technological innovation ability from immature to mature production technology, optimal investment and output efficiency, and organisational innovation and reform, is embodied in the growth of quality. The focus of the research is on resource-based entrepreneurial theories.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. 1: Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

A research design is a plan or an overall strategy for conducting the research. It is a means of ensuring that a research process is systematic and scientific enough so that the results obtained can be applied in real life (Oso and Onen, 2006). The study adopted cross section research design to establish the influence of strategic planning on growth of women owned micro and small enterprises in Kenya.

3.2 Target Population

The target population of the study consisted of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu County that have registered with Kibuye Jua Kali Association under MSE Authority. The population targeted is responsible for the entrepreneurial growth in Kenya today. From the records of Kibuye Jua Kali Association accessed on 11th September 2015, gives a target population of 295 women entrepreneurs. Table 3.1 shows the distribution of the women enterprises per trade/sector

Table 3.1: Showing Distribution of Women Enterprises per trade/sector

No	Trade/Sector	Number of Women Enterprises	Percentage (%)
1.	Textile	167	56.61
2.	Metal Fabrication	61	20.68
3.	Woodwork	20	6.78
4.	Other trades	47	15.93
Total		295	100

3.3 Sampling Frame

The sample frame for this study included all women owned MSE's at Daraja Market in the sectors of: Textile, Metal fabrication, Woodwork and Other trades

3.4 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study adopted stratified random sampling technique to establish and access the sample size. Stratified random sampling technique is useful to obtain estimates of known precision for certain subdivisions of the population by treating each subdivision as a stratum and for administrative convenience (Mugenda 2003, Kothari, 2004). Sample size of 167 respondents was adopted through the use of Krejcie and Morgan's model:

$$s = \frac{X^2 NP(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + X^2 P(1-P)}$$

s = required sample size.

X^2 = the table value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired confidence level (3.841).

N = the population size.

P = the population proportion (assumed to be .50 since this would provide the maximum Sample size)

d = the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion (.05).

$$s = \frac{3.841(295)(0.5)(1-0.5)}{0.0025(295-1) + 3.841(0.5)(1-0.5)}$$

=167 women entrepreneurs

This was distributed as shown in table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Distribution of the sample size

Category/Sector	Target Population	Sample Size	Percentage %
Textile	167	95	56.61
Metal Fabrication	61	34	20.68
Woodwork	20	11	6.78
Other Trades	47	27	15.93
	295	167	100

3.5 Data Collection Instruments

Primary and secondary data was collected. Structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data and administered by face-to-face and telephone interviews. Structured questionnaire are constructed in such a way as to require direct answers in a particular prescribed format. They facilitate consistency of responses among respondents, (Oso and Onen, 2006). Secondary data came from institutional publications and referred journals.

3.6 Pilot tests

3.6.1 Reliability of Research Instruments

Reliability is a measure of the degree to which a research instrument yields consistent results or data after repeated trials (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003, Nachmias and Nachmias, 2008). Reliability is concerned with stability and consistency in measurement. Reliability indicates consistency, or the extent to which a measure does not contain random error.

3.6.2 Validity of Research Instruments.

Validity refers to the accuracy and meaningfulness of inferences, which are based on research results (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). Validity therefore, has to do with how accurately the data obtained in the study represents the variables of the study. Robinson (2003) argues that validity means what is measured is the same as what was purported to be measured.

Expert opinion: The comments of supervisors were incorporated in the instruments as a way of improving their validity.

A pilot study: a pre test study was carried out at Kibos Market, Kisumu County-Kenya, after which the results of the pilot data analysis were used to improve validity of the instruments.

3.7 Data Analysis and Presentation

Data analysis was conducted according to the research objectives and hypothesis. Before processing the responses, data preparation was done on the completed questionnaires by editing, coding, entering and cleaning the data. Data collected was then analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize the survey data and provide immediate summary statistics for the various objectives. These included measures of central tendency and measures of relationships. In particular, Regression Analysis was used to investigate the relationship(s) that had been hypothesized amongst the variables of study. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was also used to investigate whether independent variables have combined effect on the dependent variable.

Content analysis was conducted on the data that are of qualitative nature. In conventional terms, content analysis involves description and discussion of the data. Results were presented on frequency tables, charts and graphs.

3.8 Model specification

The study used a multiple linear regression model of the form:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

Y : Growth of MSE's

X₁ : Organizational Envisioning

X₂ : Business Environment Awareness

X₃ : Strategy options

X₄ : Strategy Planning Instruments

β₀ : coefficient of intercept

β₁ - β₄ : The corresponding coefficients for the respective independent variables for Strategic planning

ε : error term

The linear regression model is based on the following assumptions; randomness of the error term, assumption of zero mean of the error term, the assumption of constant variance and assumption of normality of the variables.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Response Rate

A survey was conducted during the month of October 2015 among Women Owned Micro and Small Enterprises at Daraja Mbili Market, Kisii County- Kenya. A total of 158 structured questionnaires were distributed to the owners/managers of these enterprises. Out of the 167 questionnaires, 118 were filled and returned. This represented 71% response rate.

4.2.1 Response according to Sector

There was a hundred percent response to the questions. Majority of respondents were in the textile trade (53%), followed by other trades (20%), metal fabrication (18%) and lastly woodwork (9%).

Table 4.1: Response according to Trade/Sector

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Textile	63	53.4	53.4	53.4
Metal fabrication	21	17.8	17.8	71.2
Woodwork	10	8.5	8.5	79.7
Others	24	20.3	20.3	100.0
Total	118	100.0	100.0	

4.2.2 Response according to position held

Most of the respondents at (82%) were enterprise owners, with only (18%) being managers.

Table 4.2: Position held by respondent

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Owner	97	82.2	82.2	82.2
Manager	21	17.8	17.8	100.0
Total	118	100.0	100.0	

4.2.3 Response as to form of business ownership

From the findings, majority of respondents were sole proprietors (89.8%), with businesses operating partnerships (9.3%), and cooperatives (0.8%). There was no limited liability company amongst the respondents.

Table 4.3: Form of business ownership

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Sole proprietorship	106	89.8	89.8	89.8
Partnership	11	9.3	9.3	99.2
Cooperative	1	.8	.8	100.0
Total	118	100.0	100.0	

4.2.4 Response as to Age of Owner/Manager

The average age of the majority of the respondents was 30-35 years (31.4%), followed by 35-40 years (28%), 25-30 years (27.1%), 20-25 years (6.8%), and those above 40 years (6.8%).

Table 4.4: Age of respondent

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
20-25 yrs	8	6.8	6.8	6.8
25-30 yrs	32	27.1	27.1	33.9
30-35 yrs	37	31.4	31.4	65.3
35-40 yrs	33	28.0	28.0	93.2
Above 40yrs	8	6.8	6.8	100.0

4.2.5 Response as to Age of business

From the findings, majority of the respondents indicated an average age of the business at 5-10 years (40.7%), followed by 0-5 years (36.4%), 15-20 years (14.4%), and above 20 years (8.5%).

Table 4.5: Age of business

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-5 yrs	43	36.4	36.4	36.4
5-10 yrs	48	40.7	40.7	77.1
15-20 yrs	17	14.4	14.4	91.5
Above 20 yrs	10	8.5	8.5	100.0
Total	118	100.0	100.0	

4.2.6 Response as to Education level of Respondents

The education level for the majority of the respondents was secondary (50%), followed by primary (39%), and tertiary at a paltry 11%.

Table 4.6: Education level of respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Primary	46	39.0	39.0	39.0
Secondary	59	50.0	50.0	89.0
Tertiary	13	11.0	11.0	100.0
Total	118	100.0	100.0	

4.2.7 Response as to Professional Skills of Respondents

From the findings, only 11% of respondents had professional skills in business management, 8.5% in entrepreneurship, and 4.2% in ICT. Majority had professional skills in other areas (76.3%).

Table 4.7: Professional skills of respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Business Management	13	11.0	11.0	11.0
Entrepreneurship	10	8.5	8.5	19.5
ICT	5	4.2	4.2	23.7
Others	90	76.3	76.3	100.0
Total	118	100.0	100.0	

4.2.8 Response as to Number of Employees in the Enterprise

Majority of respondents had an average employee number of 0-5 at (96.6%), followed by 5-10 at (3.4%). This is a typical characteristic of a Micro Enterprise as defined in the study literature.

Table 4.8: Number of Employees in the Enterprise

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-5	114	96.6	96.6	96.6
5-10	4	3.4	3.4	100.0
Total	118	100.0	100.0	

4.2.9 Response as to Existence of a Formal Strategic Plan

From the findings, only 18.6% of respondents had a formal strategic plan with a larger population of 81.4% having no formal strategic plans.

Table 4.9: Existence of a formal strategic plan

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	22	18.6	18.6	18.6
No	96	81.4	81.4	100.0
Total	118	100.0	100.0	

4.3 Pilot study results

The main purpose of conducting a pilot study was to detect and remedy any possible errors in questionnaire design prior to administering the main survey (Cavana, Delahaye & Sekeran 2001; Malhotra 2004; Polit, Beck & Hungler 2005) and typically, to refine and revise the questionnaire to help ensure the validity and reliability of the measures, as well as making it more user-friendly (Flynn et al. 1990). In addition, the pre-test was also used to estimate response rates for the questionnaire and determine the sample size of the main study.

Once the research instruments were finalized, they were tried out on a sample of eleven (18) respondents selected outside the study population but with similar characteristics to the actual study population. For this study, the pilot test for the instruments was carried out at Kibos market within Kisumu county-Kenya. The rule of thumb is that at least 1% of the sample should constitute the pilot test (Cooper & Schilder, 2011).

4.3.1 Reliability and validity of research instrument.

To provide a preliminary evaluation and refinement of the measurement scales of the draft questionnaire, coefficient alpha was calculated to assess the reliability of composite variables. SPSS software version 16.0 was employed to conduct these analyses. The reliability of a measure is the consistency of the results each time the same thing is measured using Coefficient (or Cronbach's) alpha (Hair et al. 2006). Coefficient alpha is "an index of the internal consistency of the items" and also "a useful estimate of reliability" (Gregory 2000). Reliability will be high if the scale items are highly correlated. As a standard of reliability, values of coefficient alpha above 0.70 are considered to represent acceptable reliability, those above 0.80 to represent good reliability, and those above 0.90 to represent excellent reliability, (Mugenda and Mugenda 2003, Hair et al. 2006). Reliability of the instrument was carried out using Cronbach's alpha constant which is a measure of internal consistency and average correlation. The overall Cronbach's constant was 0.737 hence the instrument was reliable.

Validity refers to the accuracy and meaningfulness of inferences, which are based on research results (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). Validity therefore, has to do with how accurately the data obtained in the study represents the variables of the study. The study applied content/construct and face validity. Construct validity was assessed through various forms of correlation analysis from the results obtained in pilot tests.

4.4 Normality tests

4.4.1 Skewness and Kurtosis test for normality

The study sought to find out how well the distribution could be approximated using the normal distribution. Consequently skewness and Kurtosis was employed as shown in table 4.10. Skewness measures the deviation of distribution from symmetry and Kurtosis measures 'peakness' of the distribution (Ming'ala 2002). The values of skewness and Kurtosis should be zero in normal distribution (field 2009). Z score values for both skewness and kurtosis normally fall within -1.96 and +1.96 if P-values are 0.05 for normally distributed data. From the finding as indicated on table 4.10 it is evident that all the data for the five variables were normally distributed.

Table 4.10: Skewness and Kurtosis

Variables	Descriptive	Statistic	Std. Error	Z score
Organizational Envisioning	Std. Deviation	.96305		
	Skewness	.769	.237	
	Kurtosis	-.598	.469	
Environmental Awareness	Std. Deviation	2.04117		
	Skewness	-.205	.223	
	Kurtosis	-.921	.442	

Strategy Option	Std. Deviation	1.52750		
	Skewness	-.958	.233	
	Kurtosis	-.149	.461	
Planning Instruments	Std. Deviation	4.54048		
	Skewness	1.340	.223	
	Kurtosis	.597	.442	
Growth of MSE's	Std. Deviation	1.92640		
	Skewness	-.452	.224	
	Kurtosis	-.730	.444	

4.4.2 Outliers test

An outlier may be described as any observation far from the rest of other observation. The presence of outlier in any given data may make the data not to assume Gaussian condition that is normality condition. It is therefore important to test the presence of outliers in any given data and even remove them for normality condition to be satisfied. In this study the outlier presence was tested using box plot and the findings were given in the table 4.11.

Table 4.11: Outliers detected

Variables	Position of observed outliers	Total number of outliers
Organizational Envisioning	12,13,30,35,39,42,45,55,66,76,77,82,86,105	14
Strategy Option	1,4,16,18,19,25,29,30,31	9

4.5 Descriptive Analysis

The results of descriptive statistics were presented according to research objectives.

Table 4.12: Organizational Envisioning

Statement	D	N	A
My business has a vision for its future	1.7%	0%	98.3%
My business has a well documented vision statement shared with employees	98.0%	0.8%	10.2%
My business has a mission statement explaining enterprise purpose	88.1%	0.8%	11.0%
My business has a well stated values that guide its behaviour	87.3%	0.8%	11.9%
My business has specific goals and objectives that guide action	61.9%	0%	38.1%

D= Decreased; N= Neutral; A= Agree

From table 4.12, majority of respondents confirmed that they had a vision for their business future (98.3%). However, 98% said that their business did not have a well documented vision statement shared with employees, 88.1% did not have a mission statement explaining enterprise purpose, 87.3% did not have well stated values that guide its behaviour in the market, and 61.9% of respondents did not have specific goals and objectives that guide action. These findings generally exhibit enterprises driven without vision, mission, goals and objectives and value statements. The relationship of Organizational envisioning and growth of MSE's has been supported by past studies. Maina, and Omwenga, (2017). conducted a study in Kenya and reported in their findings that the correlation analysis results indicate the existence of a strong relationship between strategic planning and firm performance. The strategic planning steps of firm's corporate purpose were found to be positively related to company performance. Similar studies by (Bart and Hupfer, 2004; Hong and Park, 2010) have examined the relationship between mission statement and business performance. The findings show that mission statements do affect financial performance. Similar results were found in Strong's (1997), study whose findings from a study of the formulation of mission statements by UK organizations confirm a positive relationship between mission statements and firm performance.

Table 4.13: Environmental Awareness

Statement	D	N	A
My business is aware of customers and their needs	2.5%	3.4%	94.1%
My business is aware of the state of competition in the industry	0.8%	0%	99.2%
My business is aware of its own strength and weaknesses	0.8%	0%	99.2%
My business is aware of the prevailing opportunities and threats in the market	0.8%	0.8%	98.3%
My business is aware of the available human capital	1.7%	0.8%	97.5%

My business is aware of financing options available in the market	10.2%	0%	89.8%
My business is aware of Business Development Services available from government and private sector	39.0%	0.8%	60.2%
My business is aware of state of infrastructure (e.g. electricity, water, roads) in its environment	6.8%	0%	93.2%
My business is aware of Institutions supporting Micro and Small Enterprises (e.g. MSE Authority, KIRDI, KIE, County Government.)	44.1%	0.8%	55.1%
My business is aware of prevailing regulatory environment (e.g. laws, taxes, incentives, licenses)	15.3%	0.8%	83.9%

D= Decreased; N= Neutral; A= Agree

From table 4.13, 94.1% of respondents are aware of their customers and their needs, 99.2% of respondents are aware of the state of competition in the industry, 99.2% of respondents are aware of their business strengths and weaknesses, 98.3% of respondents are aware of prevailing market opportunities and threats to their businesses, 97.5% of respondents are aware of availability of human resources for their businesses, 89.8% of responses are aware of the financing options available to their businesses, 60.2% of respondents are aware of business development services offered by the government and other development partners, 93.2% of respondents are aware of state of infrastructure in the business environment, 55.1% of respondents are aware of the various institutions supporting Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya, and 83.9% of respondents are aware of the regulatory environment prevailing in Kenya. This position supports the empirical findings of Nuwagaba & Nzewi (2013), from a survey of MSE's in Mbarara Municipality in Uganda, that revealed that environmental constraints such as high taxes, limited access to market, costly and erratic electricity supply, lack of cohesion, high taxes and lack of skilled and competent human resources hinder the growth potential and performance of MSE's. Furthermore, when MSE's experience limited access to market, their growth potential is likely to decrease. Thus, access to market according to the findings is an important factor for MSE's to perform better and to grow. Managers in MSE's may need to position their firms by producing relatively high quality products and undertaking joint marketing strategies in order to penetrate differentiated market segments.

Table 4.14: Strategy Option

Statement	D	N	A
My business has implemented a strategy that seeks to provide to the market products/services with relatively lower prices than competition	30.5%	5.1%	64.4%
My business has implemented a strategy that seeks to provide to the market products/services that are unique to those of competition	5.1%	13.6%	81.4%
My business has implemented a strategy that seeks to sell products/services to a specific group (segment) of customers	13.6%	2.5%	83.9%
My business has implemented a strategy that uses new knowledge/ideas to produce customer oriented products/services	22.2%	5.1%	72.6%

D= Decreased; N= Neutral; A= Agree

From table 4.14, 64.4% of respondents agreed that their businesses has implemented a strategy of cost leadership, 81.4% of respondents implemented a strategy of differentiation, 83.9% of respondents implemented Niche strategy, while 72.6% of respondents implemented innovation strategies. This findings supports the works of Durand & Coeurderoy, (2001) that used the Miller (1985) typology, which focused on the strategies of differentiation in innovation and differentiation in marketing.

Table 4.15: Strategy Planning Instruments

Statement	D	N	A
My business has a written business plan	83.1%	0.8%	16.1%
My business uses the business plan for loan purposes	85.6%	0.8%	13.6%
My business uses business plan to operationalise its strategy	83.9%	0.8%	15.3%
My business uses business plan for other reasons	85.6%	0.8%	13.6%
My business has a marketing plan	75.4%	0%	24.6%
My business has cashflow projections	53.4%	0%	46.6%
My business has a financial plan	61.9%	0%	38.1%

D= Decreased N= Neutral A= Agree

From table 4.15, 83.1% of respondents confirmed lack of written business plan for their businesses, 85.6% do not use business plans for loan purposes, 83.9% of respondents do not use business plans to operationalize their businesses, 85.6% of respondents do not use business plans even for other reasons, 75.4% of respondents lack marketing plan for their businesses, 53.4% of respondents has no cash flow projections for their businesses, and 61.9% of respondents has no financial plan for their businesses. These finding confirms the unstructured and uncoordinated manner in which MSE's are managed. The findings also lack the support of scholars that concluded that business planning helped entrepreneurial managers to deal with larger amounts of information and to stretch their cognitive limitations (Gruber, 2007), allowed entrepreneurs to set specific milestones and specific action steps on the way to their business vision, impacted entrepreneurial persistence in building a business, securing access to necessary resources or help reduce the liability of newness (Liao & Gartner, 2006; Perry, 2001). Although there is some evidence that preparing business plans could primarily be a ceremonial issue (Honig, 2004), and that actual organizational behaviors could become loosely coupled from those stated in the plan (Karlsson & Honig, 2009), failing to prepare a business plan may erode an organization's legitimacy in the eyes of its initial resource providers, potentially strangling performance or even threatening its very existence.

Table 4.16: Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises

Statement	I	D	RC
My business has experienced a change in employee numbers	26.3%	9.3%	64.4%
My business has experienced a change in sales volume	62.7%	17.8%	19.5%
My business has experienced a change in the value of Non-current Assets	24.8%	5.1%	70.1%

I= Increased; D= Decreased; RC= Remained Constant

From table 4.16, considering the period the enterprises have been in operation, 64.4% of respondents has not experienced a change in employee numbers within their businesses, 62.7% of respondents have experienced a change in sales volume, while 70.1% of respondents have not experienced a change in the value of Non-current assets. On average therefore, these Enterprises have remained largely stagnant, an indication that some internal strategic management is welcome.

4.6 Regression Analysis

Objective One: To determine the influence of Organizational Envisioning on growth of Women owned Micro and Small Enterprises at Kibuye market kisumu county, Kenya.

Table 4.17: Goodness of Fit Model Summary-Organizational Envisioning on Growth of MSE

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.244 ^a	.059	.050	1.69064
a. Predictors: (Constant), EN				

The goodness of fit model presented in table 4.17 involves Organizational Envisioning (X_1) as the only independent variable. The coefficient of determination (R square) of 0.059 indicated that the model explained only 5.9% of the variation or change in the dependent variable, with the remainder of 94.1% being explained by other factors other than Organizational Envisioning. Adjustment of the R square did not change the results substantially, having reduced the explanatory behaviour of the predictor to 5%.

Table 4.18: Coefficients-Organizational Envisioning and Growth of MSE

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10.073	1.323		7.615	.000
	EN	-.438	.173	-.244	-2.527	.013
a. Dependent Variable: GMSE						

Table 4.18 presents the regression results of Organizational Envisioning on Growth of MSE's. With a constant (p-value = 0.000) of 10.073, the study concluded that even without Organizational Envisioning, MSE's seemed to display some form of Growth. The gradient coefficient of -0.43 indicated the extent to which a unit change in Organizational Envisioning cause a change in Growth. In this case, a unit change in Organizational Envisioning leads to 0.43 units of negative change in Growth of MSE's. This means that Organizational Envisioning was significant (p-value = 0.000) in influencing the Growth of Women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market.

Therefore, the Organizational Envisioning and Growth model can now be presented as follows:

$$Y = 10.073 - 0.43X_1 + \varepsilon.$$

Table 4.19: ANOVA Analysis- Organizational Envisioning and Growth of MSE's

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	18.247	1	18.247	6.384	.013 ^a
	Residual	288.685	101	2.858		
	Total	306.932	102			

a. Predictors: (Constant), EN

b. Dependent Variable: GMSE

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the relationship between Organizational Envisioning and Growth of MSE's is presented in table 4.19. The results with a p-value of 0.013 being less than 0.05 for the model indicates that the model is statistically significant in explaining the relationship between Organizational Envisioning and Growth of MSE's. In this regard, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) that Organizational Envisioning has no significant influence on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya. Therefore, we conclude that there is significant positive influence of Organizational Envisioning on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya.

Objective Two: To examine the influence of Environmental Awareness on growth of Women owned Micro and Small Enterprises at Kibuye market kisumu county, Kenya.

Table 4.20: Goodness of Fit Model Summary- Environmental Awareness and Growth of MSE's

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.043 ^a	.002	-.007	1.93300

a. Predictors: (Constant), EA

The goodness of fit model presented in table 4.20 involves Environmental Awareness (X_2) as the only independent variable. The coefficient of determination (R square) of 0.002 indicated that the model explained only 2% of the variation or change in the dependent variable, with the remainder of 98% being explained by other factors other than Environmental Awareness. Adjustment of the R square did not change the results substantially, having reduced the explanatory behaviour of the predictor to -7%.

Table 4.21: Coefficients- Environmental Awareness and Growth of MSE's

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.312	2.427		2.189	.031
	EA	.040	.088	.043	.457	.648

a. Dependent Variable: GMSE

Table 4.21 presents the regression results of Environmental Awareness on Growth of MSE's. With a constant (p-value = 0.000) of 5.312, the study concluded that even without Environmental Awareness, MSE's seemed to display some form of Growth. The gradient coefficient of 0.40 indicated the extent to which a unit change in Environmental Awareness cause a change in Growth. In this case, a unit change in Environmental Awareness leads to 0.40 units of positive change in Growth of MSE's. This means that Environmental Awareness was significant (p-value = 0.000) in positively influencing the Growth of Women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market.

Therefore, the Environmental Awareness on Growth model can now be presented as follows: $Y = 5.312 + 0.40X_2 + \varepsilon.$

Table 4.22: ANOVA Analysis- Environmental Awareness and Growth of MSE's

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.781	1	.781	.209	.648 ^a
	Residual	429.698	115	3.737		
	Total	430.479	116			

a. Predictors: (Constant), EA

b. Dependent Variable: GMSE

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the relationship between Environmental Awareness and Growth of MSE's is presented in table 4.22. The results with a p-value of 0.648 being greater than 0.05 for the model indicates that the model is statistically insignificant in explaining the relationship between Environmental Awareness and Growth of MSE's. In this regard, we accept the null hypothesis (H_0) that Environmental Awareness has no significant influence on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya. Therefore, we conclude that there is no significant influence of Environmental Awareness on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya.

Objective Three: To establish the influence of Strategy Options on growth of Women Owned Micro and Small Enterprises at Kibuye market kisumu county, Kenya.

Table 4.23: Goodness of Fit Model Summary- Strategy Option and Growth of MSE's

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.213 ^a	.045	.036	1.94400
a. Predictors: (Constant), SO				

The goodness of fit model presented in table 4.23 involves Strategic Options (X_3) as the only independent variable. The coefficient of determination (R square) of 0.045 indicated that the model explained only 4.5% of the variation or change in the dependent variable, with the remainder of 95.5% being explained by other factors other than Strategic Options. Adjustment of the R square did not change the results substantially, having reduced the explanatory behaviour of the predictor to 3.6%.

Table 4.24: Coefficients- Strategy Option and Growth of MSE's

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.457	1.330		2.599	.011
	SO	.276	.123	.213	2.237	.027
a. Dependent Variable: GMSE						

Table 4.24 presents the regression results of Strategic Option on Growth of MSE's. With a constant (p-value = 0.000) of 3.457, the study concluded that even without Strategic Options, MSE's seemed to display some form of Growth. The gradient coefficient of 0.276 indicated the extent to which a unit change in Strategic Option cause a change in Growth. In this case, a unit change in Strategic Option leads to 0.276 units of positive change in Growth of MSE's. This means that Strategic Options was significant (p-value = 0.000) in positively influencing the Growth of Women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market.

Therefore, the Strategic Options and Growth model can now be presented as follows:

$$Y = 3.457 + 0.276X_3 + \varepsilon.$$

Table 4.25: ANOVA Analysis- Strategic Options and Growth of MSE's

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	18.911	1	18.911	5.004	.027 ^a
	Residual	396.809	105	3.779		
	Total	415.720	106			
a. Predictors: (Constant), SO						
b. Dependent Variable: GMSE						

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the relationship between Strategic Options and Growth of MSE's is presented in table 4.25. The results with a p-value of 0.027 being less than 0.05 for the model indicates that the model is statistically significant in explaining the relationship between Strategic Options and Growth of MSE's. In this regard, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) that Strategic Options has no significant influence on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya. Therefore, we conclude that there is significant positive influence of Strategic Options on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya.

Objective Four: To determine the influence of Planning Instruments on growth of Women Owned Micro and Small Enterprises at kibuye market kisumu county, Kenya.

Table 4.26: Goodness of Fit Model Summary- Planning Instruments and Growth of MSE's

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.422 ^a	.178	.171	1.75415
a. Predictors: (Constant), PI				

The goodness of fit model presented in table 4.26 involves Planning Instruments (X_4) as the only independent variable. The coefficient of determination (R square) of 0.178 indicated that the model explained only 17.8% of the variation or change in the dependent variable, with the remainder of 82.2% being explained by other factors other than Planning Instruments. Adjustment of the R square did not change the results substantially, having reduced the explanatory behaviour of the predictor to 17.1%.

Table 4.27: Coefficients-Planning Instruments and Growth of MSE's

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.299	.410		20.230	.000
	PI	-.183	.037	-.422	-4.990	.000
a. Dependent Variable: GMSE						

Table 4.27 presents the regression results of Planning Instruments on Growth of MSE's. With a constant (p-value = 0.000) of 8.299, the study concluded that even without Planning Instruments, MSE's seemed to display some form of Growth. The gradient coefficient of -1.83 indicated the extent to which a unit change in Planning Instruments cause a change in Growth. In this case, a unit change in Planning Instruments leads to 1.83 units of negative change in Growth of MSE's. This means that Planning Instruments was significant (p-value = 0.000) in negatively influencing the Growth of Women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market.

Therefore, the Planning Instruments and Growth model can now be presented as follows: $Y = 8.299 - 1.83X_4 + \epsilon$.

Table 4.28: ANOVA Analysis- Planning Instruments and Growth of MSE's

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	76.620	1	76.620	24.901	.000 ^a
	Residual	353.859	115	3.077		
	Total	430.479	116			
a. Predictors: (Constant), PI						
b. Dependent Variable: GMSE						

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the relationship between Planning Instruments and Growth of MSE's is presented in table 4.28. The results with a p-value of 0.000 being less than 0.05 for the model indicates that the model is statistically significant in explaining the relationship between Planning Instruments and Growth of MSE's. In this regard, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) that Planning Instruments has no significant influence on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya. Therefore, we conclude that there is significant positive influence of Planning Instruments on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya.

Regression Analysis of the overall Model

The regression analysis of the overall model determined the influence of the independent variable-Strategic Planning on the dependent variable- Growth.

Table 4.29: Goodness of Fit Model Summary- Strategic Planning and Growth of MSE's

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.452 ^a	.204	.169	1.62493
a. Predictors: (Constant), PI, EN, EA, SO				

The significance of the model was reaffirmed by the goodness of fit tests in table 4.29 whereby the coefficient of determination (R square) of 0.204 confirmed that the model explained 20.4% of the variation or change in the dependent variable. The adjusted R square did not make any difference either, since the model now explained 16.9% of the variations.

Table 4.30: Coefficients- Strategic Planning and Growth of MSE's

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.417	2.774		1.953	.054
	EN	-.300	.181	-.162	-1.659	.101
	EA	.065	.095	.075	.679	.499
	SO	.318	.127	.280	2.513	.014
	PI	-.163	.051	-.320	-3.196	.002
a. Dependent Variable: GMSE						

The linear regression analysis presented in table 4.30 indicated that regression coefficients were significant in explaining the relationship between each of the four independent variables. It also confirmed the significant roles of the four variables in the growth of women owned Micro and Small Enterprises at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya.

The interpretation of these results was that the contributions of the variables were two variables positive and two variables negative. That is, there was a significant relationship between Strategic planning and Growth of MSE's.

The model can be represented as follows:

$$Y = 5.417 - 0.300X_1 + 0.065X_2 + 0.318X_3 - 0.163X_4$$

Where X_1 = Organizational Envisioning

X_2 = Environmental Awareness

X_3 = Strategy Options

X_4 = Planning Instruments

Table 4.31: ANOVA Analysis- Strategic Planning and Growth of MSE's

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	60.377	4	15.094	5.717	.000 ^a
	Residual	234.996	89	2.640		
	Total	295.372	93			
a. Predictors: (Constant), PI, EN, EA, SO						
b. Dependent Variable: GMSE						

The ANOVA analysis in table 4.31 presents the influence of all the independent variables on Growth of MSE's at Kibuye Market. The results with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, indicated that the model was statistically significant in explaining the influence of strategic Planning on Growth of Women owned MSE's at Kibuye market, Kisumu county. It was, therefore, concluded that Strategic Planning had a significant combined influence on Growth of Women owned MSE's at Kibuye market, Kisumu county.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The target population was women owned MSE's at Daraja Mbili market who stood at 450 in number. A stratified random sampling was adopted where the enterprises were categorized in four strata: textile, metal fabrication, woodwork and other trades. A structured questionnaire was used to collecting data. Out of 167 respondents given the questionnaire 118 respondents accounting for 71% completed and returned the questionnaire. This was considered adequate response, as espoused by Mugenda and mugenda (2003). Pilot testing was done using a sample of 18 questionnaires where reliability and validity was performed. This helped improve the research instrument greatly.

5.1.1 Organizational Envisioning and Growth of SME's

From the results of the descriptive analysis most respondents (83.8%) agreed that their enterprises have not laid done and effective communicated organizational direction (vision, mission, goals and objectives and value), even though 98.3% claim unwritten vision for their enterprise future. Moreover from the analysis of variance carried out, it was clear that there was a significant relationship between Organizational Envisioning and Growth with $p\text{-value} = 0.013 < 0.05$, hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies the more owners/managers of MSE's got involved with organizational envisioning the higher the possibility of creating and sustaining growth in their markets. Moreover the findings of the regression models showed a positive influence between the variables of study ($Y = 10.073 - 0.43X_1$).

5.1.2 Environmental Awareness and Growth of SME's

From the results of the descriptive analysis most respondents (87%) agreed that their enterprises are aware of the prevailing business environment. Moreover from the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the relationship between Environmental Awareness and Growth of MSE's carried out at $p\text{-value} = 0.648$ which is greater than 0.005, it was clear that there is no significant influence of Environmental Awareness on Growth of women owned MSE's at Kibuye Market, Kisumu county-Kenya. The study thus failed to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that although environmental awareness is an important activity in strategic planning, reconciling environmental variables/information to strategic orientation of a firm would be much more valuable to the owners/managers of MSE. Moreover the findings of the regression model showed a positive influence between environmental awareness and growth ($Y = 5.312 + 0.40X_2$).

5.1.3 Strategy Option and Growth of SME's

From the results of the descriptive analysis most respondents (75.6%) implemented business strategies of cost leadership, differentiation, niche and innovation. Moreover from the analysis of variance carried out, it was clear that there was a significant relationship between strategy options and Growth with $p\text{-value} = 0.027 < 0.05$, hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies the more owners/managers of MSE's focused on either of the business strategies or a combination of all, the higher the possibility of creating and sustaining growth in their markets. Each business strategy is capable of delivering the market to an enterprise when carefully executed. The findings of the regression model showed a positive influence between strategy option and growth of MSE's ($Y = 3.457 + 0.276X_3$).

5.1.4 Planning Instruments and Growth of SME's

From the results of the descriptive analysis most respondents (76%) do not have strategic planning instruments (business plan, marketing plan and financial plan).

However, from the analysis of variance carried out, it was clear that there was a significant relationship between planning instruments and Growth with $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$, hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies the owner's/manager's of MSE's should develop and make use of the planning instruments so as to create and sustain growth in their markets. The findings of the regression model showed a negative influence between planning instruments and growth of MSE's ($Y = 8.299 - 1.83X_4$).

5.2 Conclusion

This study provides evidence that strategic planning does matter in MSE growth. Vision is an important element of strategic management, and as shown in this study, exact formulation of the vision statement and strategy formulation can be beneficial for small firm growth. Interestingly, our findings indicate that MSE owners have a vision in their minds but not shared amongst organizational members. This is reflected in their lack of a well stated and communicated vision, mission and value statements.

In addition to vision, environmental awareness, strategic options and planning instruments have also been shown to be crucial strategy planning drivers of small firm's growth. We obtained also one puzzling result: about three quarter of entrepreneurs reported to not having any planning instrument. This could be linked to their educational and professional skill levels that were secondary and others respectively. It may mean that entrepreneurs recognize the importance of education for the development of their enterprises, but that the efficiency of management and entrepreneurship education may be very low.

Finally, the study provided some empirical evidence that the extent of use of strategic planning practices (such as knowledge about opportunities and threats in the market, Knowledge about own strengths and weaknesses, knowledge about institutional and regulatory environment and the orientation of all employees towards the common goal) and generic strategies (differentiation, cost leadership, and focus/niche strategy) can be predictive of small firm growth. Our findings which are that small firms tend to rely on differentiation and focus/niche business strategy more than on cost leadership strategy and innovation seem to be the result of a common characteristic of small firms, which in comparison to large firms have lesser resources and lesser opportunity and capability to compete on the basis of economies of scale.

The study has practical implications. Entrepreneurs need to be aware that strategic planning practices, processes and techniques can be beneficial for growth of the firm. In order to enable their firms to grow, entrepreneurs may like to consider exactly formulating vision and strategy, focus on growth, profit, and market; among strategic analysis techniques pay special attention to analysis of market and competition, and exactly formulate generic business strategies. All these strategic planning efforts need to be reinforced by practices that follow the key growth and market orientations, and have enterprise wide support.

5.3 Recommendations

In view of the findings as well as the conclusion deduced from the study some recommendations were made. Firstly, the study suggests that institutional support should be extended to the MSE sector to help build capacity of the owners/Managers as far as strategic planning is concerned. The recently created MSE Authority in Kenya should urgently provide this support as stipulated in the MSE Act of 2012. Secondly, the MSE owners/managers through their associations should encourage networking amongst its members in order to learn best practices which include developing strategic plans. The development partners in their efforts to spur entrepreneurship in Kenya should support programs that will create awareness and attitude change among entrepreneurs as to the benefits of strategic planning in business.

5.4 Areas of further research

The generalizability of the findings may be limited because data collection was conducted within only one market in the Kenyan economy. Therefore, cross cultural comparisons can reinforce current findings and bring new insights to future research. The focus of the study was predominantly on strategic planning, and did not include other strategic management elements, such as implementation and control issues, which would be of interest for future research. Data was collected from women owned enterprises only. Using both genders may increase reliability in future research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aldrich, H.E. (1999). *Organisations Evolving*. Sage Publications
- [2] Waweru, P. K., & Omwenga, J. (2015). The influence of strategic management practices on performance of private construction firms in Kenya. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 5(6), 1-36.
- [3] Maina, M. C., & Omwenga, J. (2017). Factors influencing implementation of strategic plans in state corporations in kenya: a case study of kenya coconut development authority, mombasa. *Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 4(4).
- [4] Aldrich, H.E., & Cliff, J. (2003), "The pervasive effects of familyon entrepreneurship: toward a family embeddedness perspective", *Journal of Business Venturing*, 18,573-596.
- [5] Allinson, C., Chell, E., & Hayes, J. (2000). Intuition and entrepreneurial behavior. *EuropeanJournal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 9(1), 31- 43.
- [6] Altenburg, T. and von Drachenfels, C. (2006) 'The "New Minimalist Approach" to Private-SectorDevelopment: A Critical Assessment', *Development Policy Review* 24: 387-411.
- [7] Alvarez, S., & Busenitz, L. (2001), "The entrepreneurship of resource based theory", *Journal of Management*, 27,755-775.
- [8] Anderson, A., & Miller, C. (2003), "Class matters: human and social capital in the entrepreneurialprocess", *The Journal of Socio-Economics*, 32, 17-36.

- [9] Ansoff, H.I. (1965): Corporate strategy: An analytic approach to business policy for growth and expansion, New York: McGraw Hill.
- [10] Bamberger, I., (1980). "Development and Growth of Firms - A Theoretical Frame of Reference of Research Project Concerning Small and Medium Firms", Unpublished paper, University of Rennes, in Gibb, A.A., Scott, M., Strategic Awareness, Personal Commitment and the Process of Palling in the Small Business, *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol.22, No.6, 1980, pp. 597-631.
- [11] Bannock, G., Matthew, G., & Mariell, J.A., (2002). 'Indigenous Private Sector Development and Regulation in Africa and Central Europe: A 10 Country Study', London: Bannock Consulting.
- [12] Accessed from <http://www.dai.com/pdf/IndigenousPrivateSectorDevelopment.pdf> (on 9 December 2011).
- [13] Baum, J.R., Locke, E.A., & Smith, K.G. (2001): "A multidimensional model of venture growth", *Academy of Management Journal*, 44, 292-303
- [14] Bart, C., Hupfer, M. (2004), Mission Statements in Canadian Hospitals, *J. Health Organ. Manage.* 18(2).
- [15] Beal, R.M. (2000). Competing effectively: Environmental scanning, competitive strategy & organizational performance in small manufacturing firms. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 38(1): 27-47.
- [16] Becker, (1975), "Human Capital. Chicago", IL: Chicago University Press.
- [17] Berman, J., Gordon, D., and Sussman, G. (1997). "A study to determine the benefits small business firms derive from sophisticated planning versus less sophisticated types of planning." *The Journal of Business and Economic Studies* 3(3): 1-11.
- [18] Bhide, A. (2000). The Origin and Evolution of New Businesses. New York: Oxford University Press.
- [19] Boag, D.A. and Dastmalchian, A. (1988): "Growth strategies and performance in electronic companies", *Industrial Market Management*, 17: 329-336
- [20] Blanchard K., Stoner, J. (2004). The Vision Thing: Without It You'll Never Be a World-Class Organization. *Leader to Leader*, 2004. 31, Winter. pp. 21-28.
- [21] Blanchflower, D., Oswald, A., & Stutzer, A. (2001), "Latent entrepreneurship across nations?" *European Economic Review*, 45, 680-691.
- [22] Block, Z., & MacMillan, I.C. (1985). Milestones for successful venture planning. *Harvard Business Review* (September-October), 63, 184-196.
- [23] Bracker, J.S., Keats, B.W. and Pearson, J.N., (1988). "Planning and financial performance among small firms in a growth industry", *Strategic Management Journal*, (9), pp.591-603.
- [24] Brinckmann, J., Grichnik, D., & Kapsa, D. (2010). Should entrepreneurs plan or just storm the castle? A meta-analysis on contextual factors impacting the business planning-performance relationship in small firms. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 25, 24-40.
- [25] Carlsson, et.al., (1984). Differentiating Entrepreneurs from Small Business Owners, *The Academy of Management Review*, 9(2), 354-359
- [26] Carter, N., Gartner, W., & Reynolds, P. (1996). Exploring start-up event sequences. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 11, 151-166.
- [27] Castrogiovanni, G.J., (1996). "Pre-start up planning and the survival of new small businesses: theoretical linkages", *Journal of Management*, 22 (6), 801-822.
- [28] CBS, ICEG, K-rep Holdings. (1999). Kenya National Micro and Small Enterprise Baseline Survey. Nairobi: CBS.
- [29] Chandler, G., & Hanks, S. (1998). "An examination of the substitutability of founder's human and financial capital in emerging business ventures", *Journal of Business Venturing*, 13, 353-369.

- [30] Commander, S., and Svejnar, J. (2007), 'Do Institutions, Ownership, Exporting and Competition Explain Firm Performance? Evidence from 26 Transition Countries.' Institute for the Study of Labor (IZA) Discussion Paper 2637.
- [31] Coulter, M. 2003. *Entrepreneurship in Action*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [32] Clausen, T.H. (2006), "Who identifies and Exploits entrepreneurial opportunities", Retrieved from www.ccsr.ac.uk
- [33] Clayton, C. M. (1997): *The Innovator's Dilemma: When New Technologies Cause GreatFirms to Fail*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- [34] Dalberg Global Development Advisors, (2011). Report on Support to SMEs in Developing Countries Through Financial Intermediaries, November 2011
- [35] Davidson, P., & Honing, B. (2003), "The role of social and human capital among nascent entrepreneurs", *Journal of Business Venturing*, 20,121.
- [36] Deakins, D., Freel, M. (2003), "Entrepreneurship and small firm", Mc Graw-Hill publication, New York
- [37] Delmar, F., & Shane, S. (2004). Legitimizing first: organizing activities and the survival of new ventures. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 19, 385- 410.
- [38] Dethier, J., Hirn, M., & Straub, S. (2010). Explaining enterprise performance in developing countries with business climate survey data, *The World Bank Research Observer*, 26, 258–309.
- [39] Djankov, S., La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, & Shleifer, A. (2002). The regulation of entry. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 117(1), 1-37.
- [40] Djankov, S., La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes & Shleifer, A. (2003). Courts, *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(2), 453-517.
- [41] Doty, D.H., Glick, W.H. (1994), "Typologies as a unique form of theory building: toward improved understanding of modeling", *Academy of Management Review*, 19(2): 230-251
- [42] Deya, J., Omwenga, J., & Muturi, W. (2015). Influence of Strategic Planning on Growth of Women Owned Micro and Small Enterprises in Kibuye Market, Kisumu County-Kenya. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 5(11), 2222-6990.
- [43] Durand, R. & Coeurderoy, R. (2001): "Age, order of entry, strategic orientation, and organizational performance", *Journal of Business Venturing*, 16: 471-494
- [44] Dranove, D., and Shanley, M., and Simon, C. (1992). "Is Hospital Competition Wasteful?", *RAND Journal of Economics*, v 23 (2), pp 247-262.
- [45] Drucker, P. F. (2001). *Management challenges for the 21st century*. New York: Harper Business.
- [46] Evans, D., & Jovanovic, B. (1989), "An Estimated Model of Entrepreneurial Choice under Liquidity Constraints", *The Journal of Political Economy*, 97, 808-827.
- [47] European Commission. (2005). *Flash Eurobarometer: SME access to finance*. Bruxelles, Belgium.
- [48] Finkelstein, S., Hambrick, D., Cannella, A., (2009). *Strategic Leadership: Theory and Research on Executives, Top Management Teams, and Boards*. Oxford University Press: Oxford, U.K.
- [49] Gartner, W. B., Shaver, K. G., Carter, N. M., & Reynolds, P. D. (2004). *The Handbook of Entrepreneurial Dynamics: The Process of Organization Creation*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications
- [50] Gibb, A.A., Scott, M., (1985). Strategic Awareness, Personal Commitment and the Process of Palling in the Small Business, *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol.22, No.6, 1985, pp.597-631
- [51] Gibbons, P.T. & O'Connor, T. (2005): "Influences on strategic planning processes among Irish SMEs", *Journal of Small Business Management*, 43(2), 170-186

- [52] Gibson, B., & Cassar, G. (2002) 'Planning behavior variables in small firms', *Journal of Small Business Management*, 40: 171-86.
- [53] Gibson, B., & Cassar, G. (2005). 'Longitudinal Analysis of Relationships between Planning and Performance in Small Firms', *Small Business Economics*, 25 (3), 207- 222.
- [54] Government of Kenya (GoK), (2004). Economic survey, 2004, Central Bureau of Statistics, Ministry of planning and National Development, Government Printers, Nairobi.
- [55] Gruber, M. (2007). Uncovering the value of planning in new venture creation: a process and contingency perspective. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 22, 782-807.
- [56] Haberberg, A., & Rieple, A. (2008). *Strategic Management - Theory and Application*: Oxford University Press.
- [57] Hodegetts, R.M., Kuratko, D.F., (2001). *Effective Small Business Management*, Dryden, Fort Worth, TX, 2001.
- [58] Honig, B. (2004). Entrepreneurship education: Toward a model of contingency-based business planning. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 3(3), 258-273.
- [59] Honig, B., & Samuelsson, M. (2012). Planning and the entrepreneur: a longitudinal examination of nascent entrepreneurs in Sweden. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 50(3), 365-388.
- [60] Holtz-Eakin, D., Joulfaian, D., & Rosen, H, S. (1994), "Sticking it out: Entrepreneurial Survival and Liquidity Constraints, *Journal of Political Economy*, 1,102
- [61] Hurst, E., & Lusardi, A. (2004), "Liquidity Constraints, Household Wealth, Entrepreneurship, *Journal of Political Economy*, 2,112
- [62] International Labour Organization, (2002). *Small enterprises, big challenges a literature review on the impact of the policy environment on the creation and improvement of jobs within small enterprises*. Geneva, Switzerland:
- [63] International Labour Organization, (1998). *Job Creation in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises. Recommendation 189 in the subject of Employment Policy and Promotion. General Conference of the International Labor Organization*. Geneva, Switzerland.
- [64] Ireland, D., Hitt, A. (2007). Achieving and maintaining strategic competitiveness in the 21st century: The role of strategic leadership. *Acad. Manage. Exec.* 19 (4): 63-77.
- [65] Ireland, R. D., Hitt, M.A., & Sirmon, D.G. (2003): "A model of strategic entrepreneurship: The construct and its dimensions", *Journal of Management*, 29(6): 963-989
- [66] Jorosi, B.N. (2008). Environmental scanning in Botswana's SMEs: A study of the manufacturing industry. *Libri*, 58, 224-233.
- [67] Julien, P.A. (1998) (ed.), *The State of the Art in Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, Aldershot: Ashgate.
- [68] Kantabutra, S., Avery, G. C. (2010). "The power of vision: Statements that resonate", *The Journal of Business Strategy*, 31(1), pp. 37-45.
- [69] Karlsson, T., & Honig, B. (2009). Judging business by its cover: an institutional perspective on new ventures and the business plan. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 24(1), 27-45.
- [70] Keogh, W., & Evans, G. (1998), "Strategies for Growth and the Barriers faced by new technology-based SMEs", *Journal of small business and enterprise development*, 5(4): 337-350
- [71] Kim, P., Aldrich, H.E., & Keister, L.A. (2003). Access (not) denied: The Impact of financial, human and cultural capital on becoming a Nascent Entrepreneur. Working paper.
- [72] Klapper, L., Lewin, A., & Quesada, J. (2009). The impact of the business environment on the business creation process, *Policy Research Working Paper*, 4937, The World Bank.
- [73] Knott, A. M., & Wu, B. (2006) .Entrepreneurial Risk and Market Entry, *Management Science*, 52 (9), pp. 1315-1330.

- [74] Kothari, C.R. (2004). *Research Methodology Methods & Techniques*. (2nd ed.). New Delhi: New Age International publisher.
- [75] Korunka, C., Frank, H., Lueger, M., & Mugler, J. (2003), "The entrepreneurial personality in the context of resources, environment, and the startup process-A configurational approach", *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 28(1), 23-42
- [76] Kutlovci E., & Shala V. (2011). The impact of strategic planning on small business growth in Kosovo. *Journal of Business and Economics*, 2(1), 66-72.
- [77] Shikuku, D. N., & Omwenga, J. (2015). Determinants of Performance of Group Owned Enterprises in the Dairy Industry in Trans-Nzoia County. *Strategic Journal of Business and Change Management*, 2(95), 1385-1405.
- [78] Kraus, S., Harms, R. & Schwarz, E. (2008), "Strategic business planning and success in small firms", *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 8(4), pp. 381-396.
- [79] Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 30, 607-610.
- [80] Lerner, M. & Almor, T. (2002). Relationships among strategic capabilities and the performance of women-owned small ventures. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 40, 109-125.
- [81] Levin, M. L. (2000). Vision revisited, *The Journal of Applied Behavioural Science*, 36, 91- 107
- [82] Loayza, N., Oviedo, A., & Servén, L. (2010). Regulation and Macroeconomic Performance. In N. Loayza & Servén, L. (Eds.), *Business Regulation and Economic Performance*, (pp. 65-117). Washington, DC: The World Bank e-library.
- [83] Leonard-Barton, D. (1992) Core capabilities and core rigidities: A paradox in managing new product development, *Strategic Management Journal*. 13, 111-125.
- [84] Lobontiu, M. & Lobontiu, G. (2001), *Management strategic in intreprinderile micro si mici*(Strategic Management in micro- and small enterprises), in: Conferinta Jubiliara de Comunicari Stiintifice "Mirabila Samanta", Alba Iulia: Academia Informatizata pentru Stiinte Tehnice, Economice, de Drept si Administratie "Ion I. C. Bratianu", Centrul Universitar Alba Iulia, 26-27 octombrie.
- [85] Liao, J., & Gartner, W.B. (2006). The effects of pre-venture plan timing and perceived environmental uncertainty on the persistence of emerging firms. *Small Business Economics*, 27, 23- 40.
- [86] Lyles, M.A., Baird, I.S., Orris, J.B. & Kuratko, D.F. (1993) 'Formalized planning in small business: Increasing strategic choices', *Journal of Small Business Management*, 31(2): 38-50.
- [87] MacGregor, D. (1999), "Leadership and Strategy Challenges", in: F. Dawes (ed.), *Small Business Management*, Dublin: Blackhall Publishing, pp. 139-163.
- [88] Majumdar, S. (2008): "Modelling Growth Strategy in Small Entrepreneurial Business Organisations", *Journal of Entrepreneurship*; 17: 157-168
- [89] Mascarenas, B., Kumaraswamy, A., Day, D. & Baveja, A. (2002): "Five strategies for rapid growth and how to implement them", *Managerial and Decisions Economics*, 23(4): 317-330
- [90] Matthews, C.H., & Scott, S.G. (1995). Uncertainty and planning in small and entrepreneurial firms: an empirical assessment. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 33(4), 34-52.
- [91] Meyer, G. D. & Heppard, K.A. (2000): *Entrepreneurship as Strategy- Competing on the Entrepreneurial Edge*, California: Sage Publications
- [92] Meyer-Stamer, J. & Haar, J. (2008). Introduction: The environment of small-enterprise competitiveness. In J. Haar & Meyer- Stamer J. (Eds.), *Small Firms, Global Markets* (pp. 3-17). New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan.
- [93] Miller C. C. and Cardinal L. B. (2001), "Strategic planning and firm performance", *Management Review*, 43 (Winter): 139-160.

- [94] Miller C. C. and Cardinal L.B. (1994), “Strategic planning and firm performance: A synthesis of more than two decades of research”, *The Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 37, No. 6, pp. 1649-1665.
- [95] Mintzberg H. (1987), “The strategy concept I: Five Ps for strategy”, *California Management Review*, Vol. 30, No. 1, pp. 11-24.
- [96] Moreno, A. M. & Castillas, J.C. (2008): “Entrepreneurial orientation and growth of SMEs: a causal model”, *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 32(3): 507-528
- [97] Mugenda, M.O., Mugenda, G.A. (1999). *Research Methods: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. Nairobi: Central Graphics Services.
- [98] Mugenda, O.M., Mugenda, A.G. (2003) *Research Methods: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*, Nairobi Acts Press.
- [99] Nachmias, C.F., Nachmias, D. (2008). *Research Methods in the Social Sciences*. 5th edition. Holder Education UK.
- [100] NBSSI (1990), “Supporting Micro & Small Scale Enterprises”. A handbook on Enterprise Development Part 1. NBSSI, Print Solutions, Accra.
- [101] Njoroge W. L. (2015). The influence of strategic planning on performance of small and medium enterprises in Kenya. *The Strategic Journal of Business and Change Management* 2(26), 503-515.
- [102] Norman, M. S., & Thomas, W. Z. (2003). *Effective Small Business Management: An Entrepreneurial Approach*. New Jersey.
- [103] Nuwagaba A., & Nzewi H. (2013). Major Environmental Constraints on Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Uganda: A survey of selected Micro and Small Enterprises in Mbarara Municipality. *International Journal of Cooperative Studies*, 2(1), 26-33.
- [104] Omwenga Q., J.; Mukulu E. & Kanali C. (2013). Business Networking and Performance of Women-Led Enterprises: An Empirical Investigation in Nairobi County, Kenya. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research*.
- [105] Oso, W.Y., & Onen, D. (2005). *A General Guide to Writing Research Proposal and Reports*. A book for beginning Researchers, (2nd ed.). Makerere University press. Kampala, Uganda.
- [106] Orodho, A. J. (2003). *Essentials of Educational and Social Sciences Research Method*. Nairobi: Masola Publishers.
- [107] Parker, S.C. (2004). *The economics of Self-Employment and Entrepreneurship*, Cambridge. Cambridge University Press.
- [108] Perry S. C. (2001), “The relationship between written business plans and failure of small business in the US”, *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol. 39, No. 3, pp. 201-208.
- [109] Porras, J.I & Collins J.C., (1994). *Built to Last: Successful Habits of Visionary Companies*. –New York: Harper Business, 1994.
- [110] Porter M. E. (1991), “Towards a dynamic theory of strategy”, *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 12, Special issue, pp. 95-117.
- [111] Reinecke, G. OECD. (2004). OECD Conference of Ministers Responsible for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs). *Promoting Entrepreneurship and Innovative SMEs in a Global Economy: Towards a More Responsible and Inclusive Globalisation*. Istanbul, Turkey.
- [112] Republic of Kenya. (1992). Sessional Paper No. 2 of 1992. *Small enterprises and Jua Kali Development in Kenya*. Kenya: Government Printer.
- [113] Republic of Kenya. (2005). Sessional Paper No. 2 of 2005. *On Development of Micro and Small Enterprises for Wealth and Employment Creation and Poverty reduction*. Kenya: Government Printer.

- [114] Republic of Kenya. (2000). *Symposium Report on Regional East Africa Jua ali /Nguvu Kazi Exhibition*. Ministry of Labour and Human Resources Development. Nairobi: Government Printer.
- [115] Reynolds, P.D. (1991), "Sociology and entrepreneurship: concepts and contributions", *Entrepreneurship: Theory & Practice*, 16(2), 47-70
- [116] Robinson, V. (2003). Teachers as researchers: A professional necessity? 1, 27–29.
- [117] Rue, L.W. & Ibrahim, N.A., (1998). "The Relationship between Planning Sophistication and Performance in Small Businesses", *Journal of Small Business Management*, 36 (4), pp. 24-32.
- [118] Sachs, J. 2005. *The End of Poverty*. The Penguin Press.
- [119] Sandu, P. (1997), *Management pentru intreprinzatori (Management for Entrepreneurs)*, Bucuresti: Editura Economica.
- [120] Sarasvathy, S.D. (2001). Causation and effectuation: Towards a theoretical shift from economic inevitability to entrepreneurial contingency. *Academy of Management Review*, 26(2), 243–288.
- [121] Sarasvathy, S.D. (2008). *Effectuation: Elements of entrepreneurial expertise*. New horizons in entrepreneurship research. Cheltenham, U.K.: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- [122] Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2003): *Research Methods for Business Students* (3rd), Prentice Hall.
- [123] Sekaran, U. (2004). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building Approach*. Kundli: John Willey and Sons.
- [124] Sexton, D.L. & Bowman-Upton, N.B. (1991): *Entrepreneurship: Creativity and Growth*, New York: Macmillan
- [125] Schneider, F. (2003), "The Shadow Economy", in: C. Rowley and F. Schneider (eds.), *Encyclopedia of Public Choice*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht.
- [126] Schwenk, C.R., Shrader, C.B., (1994). Effects of Formal Strategic Planning on Financial Performance in Small Firms, A Meta – Analysis, *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 17(3), pp.53-64.
- [127] Scott, W. R. (1981): *Organizations: Rational, natural, and open systems*, Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [128] Shane, S.A. (2003). *A General Theory of Entrepreneurship: The Individual-Opportunity Nexus*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar
- [129] Shane, S. A. (2000), "Prior Knowledge and the discovery of entrepreneurial opportunities", *Organisation Science*, 11, 448-469.
- [130] Shane, S.A & Venkataraman, S. (2000), "The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research", *Academy of Management Review*.
- [131] Shleifer, A. 2005. Understanding regulation, *European Financial Management*, 11(4), 439– 451.
- [132] Smallbone, D., Leigh, R., and North, D. (1995): "The Characteristics and Strategies of High Growth SMEs", *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 1(3): 44-62
- [133] Steiner, G.A.,(1967). Approaches to Long Range Planning for Smaller Business, *California Management Review*, Vol.10, No.01, 1967, pp.3-16.
- [134] Storey, D.J. (1994): *Understanding the small business sector*, London: Routledge
- [135] Sije, A., Omwenga, J. Q., & Iravo, M. (2016). Relationship between Reorganization Turnaround Strategy and Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya. *Journal of Business and Management*, 18(09), 134-138.
- [136] Sun, R., & Zhang, X. (2004). Top-down versus bottom-up learning in cognitive skill acquisition. *Cognitive Systems Research*, 5, 63–89.
- [137] Tapinos, E., Dyson, R.G., & Meadows, M. (2005). The Impact of Performance Measurement in Strategic Planning, *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol.54, No.5/6, 2005, pp.370-384.

- [138] Thompson, A. A., and Strickland, A. J. (2001). *Strategic Management: Concepts and cases*. 12th ed. Boston, MA: McGraw-Hill / Irwin.
- [139] Thorsten, B. & Demirgüç-Kunt, A. (2004). Do pro-SMEs policies work? View point note 29898, Public policy for the private sector. : The World Bank, Washington, DC.
- [140] Tybout, J. (2000). Manufacturing Firms in Developing Countries: How Well Do They Do, and Why? *Journal of Economic Literature*, American Economic Association, 38(1), 11-44.
- [141] UN Secretariat. (1997). *Public-Private Partnerships: The Enabling Environment for Development*. United Nations. New York, USA.
- [142] Ungerer, M., Pretorius, M., Herholdt, J. (2007), *Viable Business Strategies: A systematic, people-Centric approach*. 2nd Edition.
- [143] Upton, N., Teal, E.J., & Felan, J.T. (2001). Strategic and business planning practices of fast growth family firms. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 39(1), 60-72.
- [144] Valliere, D. and Peterson, R. (2009), *Entrepreneurship and Economic Growth: Evidence from Emerging and Developed Countries*, *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 21 (5-6), 459-480.
- [145] . Watts, G., Cope, J. and Hulme, M. (1998): “Ansoff’s Matrix, Pain and Gain”, *International Journal of Entrepreneurship Behaviour and Research*, 4(2): 101-111
- [146] Wheelen, T. L., & Hunger, J. D. (2008). *Strategic management and business policy: concepts and cases*. Eleventh edn., Pearson Prentice Hall, NJ.
- [147] Weiss, J. (2013). *Strategic Industrial Policy and Business Environment Reform: Are they compatible? Working Paper*. Donor Committee for Enterprise Development.
- [148] Wickham, P. A. (1998). *Strategic entrepreneurship*. London: Pitman.
- [149] World Bank. (2008). *Republic of Bolivia – policies for increasing firms’ formality and productivity*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- [150] World Bank. (2005). *World Development Report: A Better Investment Climate for Everyone*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- [151] World Bank. (2003). *Small and medium enterprises, growth and poverty: cross-country evidence*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- [152] World Bank. (2012a). *World Development Report 2013: Jobs*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- [153] World Bank. (2012b). *Doing Business 2011-2012*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.